

FROM SEA TO CYBERSPACE

Securing Europe in the Quantum Era

Webinar agenda

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Securing Europe in the Quantum Era

A joint workshop by PQ-REACT & SMAUG EU projects

Tuesday 5th of May @12:00-13:30 CET

[REGISTRATION](#)

Agenda

Time	Topic	Description
12:00-12:30	Introduction and overview of SMAUG & PQ-REACT projects	<p>PQ-REACT is a European research and innovation project focused on enabling a secure and practical transition from today's cryptographic systems to post-quantum cryptography.</p> <p>SMAUG's primary goal is to improve the underwater detection of threats in ports and their entrance routes by means of an integrated system.</p>
12:30-13:00	Cybersecurity threats in critical infrastructure	<p>The threat landscape for critical infrastructures such as energy networks, telecommunications, smart grids, and digital services. The session will present how the PQ-REACT project addresses these risks through post-quantum cryptography, cryptographic agility, migration planning, and validation tools designed to help organisations transition from vulnerable classical systems to quantum-resistant security frameworks while maintaining operational resilience in critical environments.</p>
13:00 -13:30	How the results of both projects will assist the day-to-day life of LEAs	<p>This session outlines the how the results of the project will benefit and assist law enforcement agencies and other stakeholders</p>